

**SCAFFOLDING PLAN FOR ADMINISTRATIVE CULTURE
AND PERFORMANCE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS**

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Abstract

Introduction: School management and leadership are crucial. Leadership and administration in schools today are urgent, serious, and difficult as it struggles to meet schooling expectations. This study determined and analyzed the administrative culture in terms of instructional leadership competence and administrative skills of school heads as well as the performance of public elementary schools, after which a scaffolding plan was designed.

Methods: The study used Research and Development (R & D) as well as descriptive-correlational method of research using systematic random sampling among school heads of the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte. Three sets of instruments namely School Heads Instructional Leadership Competence Instrument (SHILCI), Administrative Skills Survey Questionnaire (ASSQ), School-Based Management Assessment, Processes and Tools (SBM-APAT) were used to gather data which were analyzed with frequency counts, means and Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Results: The public elementary school heads who are middle-aged, predominately male, married, mostly are School Principal-I, relatively young in their present position as school heads, bachelor's degree with MA units, with few trainings in administration, agreed that they are Moderately Competent in their administrative culture on instructional leadership competence and administrative skills. The public elementary schools are in maturing level of practice in the School-Based management performance. The administrative culture of school heads is significantly related to the performance of the public elementary schools.

Conclusions: Based on the results a Scaffolding Plan was prepared, validated, and proposed to enhance the administrative culture and performance of elementary schools. The Scaffolding Plan was evaluated by the panel as highly valid on its objectives, strategies, time frame, persons involved, budgetary requirements and expected outcomes.

Keywords: Administrative Culture, Instructional Leadership, Research and Development, Correlation, Administrative Skills, Scaffolding Plan

Introduction

Life in the 21st century is an era of relentless and unforecastable change. The relationship between humans and the planet that sustains it has undergone enormous transformation. The world is a dynamic entity that poses quite powerful challenges to educational managers (OECD, 2016). With the ever-increasing demand for today's globalization, transformation in the education system needs to be put in place to ensure that the nation provides the best 21st-century education to present and future generations (Amadi, 2023).

Along this line, a school organization, like any other organization, must have a strong leadership and administration. Both set the way the school organization will go. The concretization of different administrative and leadership principles and practices in school setting should harmonize and complement each other. School leadership and administration challenge everyone in the field in promoting the culture of lifelong learning and teaching. The relationship between administration and leadership as summarized by Sabag and Cohen (2022) is that leadership deals with the vision, direction, effectiveness, and results focusing on the top line, while administration deals with establishing structures and systems to focus on the bottom line to get results. Azad et al., (2017) regarded both leadership and administration as indispensable in practice while Henderson (2017) stressed the close link of both which is necessary for organizational success.

Undeniably, the importance of administration and leadership in school operations cannot just be ignored (Prachagool & Nuangchalerm, 2021). The school organization evolves with the changing times and the need for both leadership and administration today are urgent, serious, and challenging. It is grappled by different problems and pressures to address the demands of the education system. Educational institutions should strive to blaze the trail and be aggressive in coping and adapting with emerging issues and innovations to survive. This view is supported by Stoll (2019) who asserted that the school is a learning organization that must be studied which includes its relationship with its parts and the external environment. On the other hand, Darling-Hammond et al., (2019) stressed that administration of school is a complex function that requires sophistication in practice. Over the years, the dynamism of educational landscape necessitates a bigger job for all the stakeholders. A new school environment calls for decentralization for more school autonomy and accountability, improvement of student achievement results and implementation of pedagogical processes including a wider responsibility for local communities and public services (Krantz & Downey, 2021). All these aspects aim to meet the educational demands of the 21st century.

Successful school administrators should then be responsive in fortifying necessary skills to create the best teaching and learning environment (Leatherman, 2022). The evolving needs of a school organization grow out of the never-ending pressure from the different stakeholders in the educational system (Chudy et al., 2021). The capacity to perform both as leaders and managers shapes the school organization. The call for enhancing leadership and administrative competencies of school heads as the most influential persons in promoting reform, change, and innovations in performing these functions poses a great challenge to educational leaders (Stasewitsch et al., 2022). The emerging changes in leading and administering organizations should be dealt with by discovering new opportunities and threats attached to these and at the same time reconciling these with essential management processes. One must understand the vibrancy of school environment, but the application of proven fundamentals of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling remain unchanged. They are as relevant as they were years ago, but their form continuously evolves. Successful school heads' leadership and administration can be developed and expanded over time. Their ability to reflect on their own actions and perceptions and those of the people around them are necessary to recognize one's endeavor to be effective and efficient. What schools need now is

not just putting the right persons in the position but equipping them with competencies that enhance and sustain a fruitful and meaningful learning environment.

In the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte, much have been done by school heads. However, despite such great efforts, results of assessments conducted by the division on school performances showed that there are gray areas that need improvement in school management and administration. Likewise, it was observed by the researcher, being a school head in the Department of Education, that instructional leadership and other administrative functions are given less attention due to overlapping activities and programs exacted by the Department. To some school heads in the elementary who are handling two or more schools, their supervisory or instructional leadership functions are often overlooked because of voluminous reports and Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) liquidations to be accomplished and submitted on time.

Accordingly, the thrust of the DepEd to empower school heads to implement school-based management has been intensified. This major trend of practice in current education reform aims at improving the quality of education services by the government and schools both public and private as well. Such a predicament provided the foundation for this study to investigate the administrative culture and performance of their respective schools.

Objectives of the Study

The study determined and analyzed the administrative culture of elementary school heads and performance of elementary schools in the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte after which a scaffolding plan was designed.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the elementary school heads in terms of the following variables: demographic characteristics as to: age, sex, and civil status; professional qualifications as to position, length of service as school heads, highest educational attainment, and number of administrative trainings undertaken?; (2) What is the prevailing administrative culture as perceived by school heads and their teachers in terms of: instructional leadership competence, and administrative skills?; (3) What is the performance of elementary schools in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources?; (4) Is there a significant relationship between the administrative culture of elementary school heads and performance of elementary schools?; (5) What scaffolding plan can be proposed to enhance the administrative culture of school heads and performance of elementary schools?; and (6) What is the content validity of the scaffolding plan in terms of: objectives, strategies, persons involved, time frame, budget and expected outcomes?

Methodology

Research Design. The study employed Research and Development (R &D) and descriptive-correlational research design. It is Research and Development (R & D) because a plan was developed to enhance the administrative culture and performance of elementary schools (Suparman et al., 2022). It is descriptive for it described the school heads' profile, administrative culture, and performance of schools. It also utilized collected data of a specific population to determine its status. On the other hand, the study is correlational because it determined and analyzed the relationship of school heads profile variables instructional leadership competence, administrative skills, and performance of elementary schools. Correlation method provides indication as to how two or more things are related to one another or how well a specific outcome might be predicted by one or more pieces of information.

Population and Sampling. The systematic random sampling was employed in the selection of respondents and considered the fifty percent plus one sample size (50% + 1) of

the school heads from various elementary schools of Division of Ilocos Norte and two teachers randomly selected as respondents. There were one hundred three (103) elementary school heads, and two hundred six (206) teachers were selected as respondents to provide quantitative data through the instruments.

Data Gathering Instrument. The study was anchored on four instruments to gather needed data. It includes the School Head Instructional Leadership Competence Instrument developed by Alsaleh (2022) with some modifications, Administrative Skills Survey Questionnaire by Mansor and Hamid (2022), the Revised School-Based Management (SBM) Framework, Assessment Process and Tool (APAT) adopted from DepEd, and the scaffolding plan validation scale adopted from the study of Burgueno et al., (2022).

The instrument developed by Gedifew (2023) measured the profile of school heads and their instructional leadership competence. It consisted of 31 items representing three dimensions of instructional leadership: defining and communicating the school goals, monitoring, and providing feedback on the teaching learning process and promoting a school-wide professional development.

Another instrument utilized was developed by Gamile & Marpa (2022) which determined the school heads' administrative skills. It is a 35-point self-assessment questionnaire. Furthermore, the Revised School-Based (SBM) Framework, Assessment Process and Tool (APAT) (DepEd Order No. 83 series 2012) was used to evaluate the performance of elementary schools grounded on the four principles of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources.

Online interviews were conducted with teachers in the elementary schools through available online platforms such as Google Meet, Zoom and Microsoft Teams to supplement quantitative data gathered and to add a greater depth of understanding. According to Yin (2003), one of the most important sources of case study information is interview. Unstructured interview questions were constructed to elicit in depth responses. All questions were open-ended in nature.

Data Gathering Procedures. Prior to conduct of the survey, communication letters were prepared to seek permission from concerned authorities to conduct the study. After the permission was obtained, online survey was administered through Google Forms to selected and identified respondents. They were given one week to answer the questionnaires. To validate the data from selected respondents, an unstructured virtual interview was done with chosen respondents. Retrieval of the questionnaires was pegged at ninety (90) percent or higher. Data on performance of the elementary schools were gathered through the School-Based Management (SBM) assessment results from year 2019 and 2020, which was assessed by a group of panel from the School Governance Operation Division (SGOD) of the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte.

Data Analysis. All quantitative data gathered through the instruments were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly using the following statistical tools: Frequency counts and percentage were used to measure the personal and professional profile of school heads. The use of weighted mean determined the final weight of each item in the instructional leadership competence, administrative skills and performance using the standardized instruments. To facilitate the interpretation of the scales and descriptive ratings used in the instruments, the following codes were utilized:

For the level of instructional competence of the school heads, the rating scale below with corresponding descriptions/interpretations was observed:

Range Interval of Mean Scores
3.51-4.00

Descriptive Interpretation
Highly Competent (HC)

2.51-3.50	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.51-2.50	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00-1.50	Not competent (NC)

For the administrative skills of school heads, the following range interval of mean scores was utilized:

3.51-4.00	High (H)
2.51-3.50	Moderately High (MH)
1.51-2.50	Slightly Low (SL)
1.00-1.50	Low (L)

To assess the results of administrative culture as to instructional leadership and administrative skills, the following rating scale was used:

3.51-4.00	Very Skillful (VS)
2.51-3.50	Moderately Skillful (MS)
1.51-2.50	Skillful(S)
1.00-1.50	Not Skillful (NS)

In determining the performance of the elementary schools, the Revised School-Based Management (SBM) Framework, Assessment Process and Tool (APAT) was used with the following rating scale:

- 3- Evidence indicates practices and procedures satisfy quality standards
- 2- Evidence indicates planned practices and procedures are fully implemented
- 1- Evidence indicates early or preliminary stages of implementation
- 0- No evidence

The level of performance of the elementary schools were categorized as to “Advance” (2.5-3.0) being the highest means accredited, “Maturing” (1.5-2.4) which manifests present practices of introducing and sustaining continuous improvement process that integrates wider community participation and significantly improve performance and learning outcomes and “Developing” (.50-1.4) which means that there is an existing developing structures and mechanisms with acceptable level and extent of community participation and impact on learning outcomes.

For the validity of the scaffolding plan, the following range of intervals of mean scores was used:

<i>Range of Interval</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.51-4.00	Highly Valid (HV)
2.51-3.50	Valid (V)
1.51-2.50	Needs Improvement (NI)
1.00-1.50	Must be Changed (MC)

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to measure if a significant relationship exists between demographic profile, instructional leadership competence, administrative skills, and performance of elementary schools.

Results and Discussion

Demographic characteristics and professional qualification. Majority of the respondents involved in the study are middle-aged, predominantly male and married. Likewise, most of the respondents are School Principals, with the length of experience as

school head within the range of 10-14 years, mostly bachelor's degree holders with MA units, and have administrative trainings for more than ten years.

Instructional leadership competence. The elementary school heads are Moderately Competent in their instructional leadership along defining and communicating school goals as perceived by themselves and their teachers with a composite mean of 3.49 and 3.50 respectively. Of all the indicators in defining and communicating school goals, school heads have a "High Competency" in ensuring that curricular materials are consistent with the school goals with weighted means of 3.82 and 3.83 respectively.

Moreover, the elementary school heads perceived themselves and their teachers that they are "Moderately Competent" in instructional leadership as to monitoring and providing feedbacks to teaching-learning process as indicated by the composite means of 3.48 and 3.49. Among the indicators, school heads are "Highly Competent" in ensuring instructional time is not interrupted with the weighted means of 3.78 and 3.79 respectively.

School heads perceived themselves to have a "High Competence" in instructional leadership as to promoting a school-wide professional development as evidenced by the composite mean of 3.51 while teachers perceived them "Moderately Competent" as obtained by the weighted mean of 3.50. This result means that school heads provide opportunities for professional development to teachers that are aligned with school goals and provides professional literature and resources to them.

Administrative skills. School heads perceived themselves to have a "Moderately High Level" of administrative skills as to communicating directives as shown by the composite mean of 3.49 while their teachers perceived that their school heads have "High Level" along this indicator as shown by the composite mean of 3.53. Taking responsibility of the decision rather than blaming others has the highest mean among the indicators as obtained by the weighted means of 3.69, while being responsive to subordinates needs rather than just own point of view has the lowest weighted means of 3.41 and 3.38 respectively.

Based on the collective responses of the respondents, the level of administrative skills of elementary school heads along motivating and inspiring was "High" as obtained by the composite mean of 3.57 and 3.53, respectively.

The composite rating given by the school heads (3.43) denoted a "Moderately High Level" of administrative skills along empowering and delegating while teachers rated higher than their school heads along this indicator as obtained by the composite mean of 3.57 with the descriptive interpretation of "High". Among the indicators, school heads registered "High Level" on helping subordinates feel competent in their task by recognizing and celebrating their successes as perceived by themselves and their teachers as obtained by the weighted means of 3.74.

School heads perceived themselves to have a "High Level" of administrative skills along with managing stress and developing resiliency based on the composite mean of 3.55 while teachers perceived them to have a "Moderately High Level" of administrative skill as obtained by the composite mean of 3.37. Among the indicators, school heads provide a high support on school priority programs and projects amidst different circumstances in its implementation accounted to internal and external factors in the workplace on a high level as obtained by the weighted mean of 3.83, although teachers perceived them to have a "Moderately High Level" on this indicator as seen by the obtained weighted mean of 3.37. On the other hand, facing adversities, difficulties and stress has the lowest mean scores of 3.49 and 3.23 respectively.

Moreover, school heads obtained a "Moderately High Level" of administrative skills along with managing conflicts as obtained by the composite means of 3.48 and 3.43 respectively. It can be noted that among the given indicators; seeking additional information and asking subordinates opinion before making decisions has the highest weighted mean of

3.53 or “High” from the school heads while their teachers rated it the lowest as indicated by the weighted mean of 3.03 or “Moderately High”.

In addition, school heads have a “High Level” of administrative skills along building effective teams and teamwork as indicated by the composite mean of 3.54 while teachers rated them “Moderately High” with the weighted mean of 3.39. It could be observed that among the indicators, encouraging group participation in making decision has the highest obtained mean score of 3.63 from the school heads while teachers rated it lowest with the mean score of 3.31.

Finally, elementary school heads have a “High Level” of administrative skills along leading positive change as obtained by the composite means of 3.65 and 3.61 respectively. Giving attention on building subordinates strengths, not just overcoming their weaknesses has the highest perceived ratings of the respondents with the weighted means of 3.83 and 3.91 while creating positive teamwork in school when interacting with subordinates has the lowest mean of 3.31 for school heads and knowing how to engage subordinates to commit envision positive change (3.21) for teachers.

Performance of elementary schools. The performance of elementary schools in the Schools Division of Ilocos Norte is in “Maturing Level” of practice as indicated by the overall mean of 1.84. The increased performance of elementary schools in the SBM from 2019-2020 signified that schools had sustained and improved a lot. The performance of school principals in public schools is crucial to the overall success of the education system (Arghode et al., 2022). Principals play a vital role in setting the tone and direction of a school, creating an environment that fosters learning and growth for students, teachers, and staff (Garcia, 2018). A high-performing principal is essential for ensuring that a school is effective in achieving its goals and providing a quality education to its students. In particular, the role of the principal in managing and leading the school is critical to improving student outcomes. This includes setting high expectations, establishing clear policies and procedures, and promoting a positive school culture. Effective principals also have a deep understanding of the educational needs of their students, and work to ensure that those needs are met through effective programs and resource allocation (Kaya & Selvitopu, 2019).

Relationship Between Administrative Culture and Performance. Instructional leadership competencies are found to be significantly related to performance along with curriculum and instruction and accountability and continuous improvement as evidenced by the obtained coefficient correlation of .213, and .214 with the p-value of .031 and .030, respectively, which are lower than 0.01 level of significance. On the other hand, leadership and governance and management of resources has no significant relationship with instructional leadership competence as obtained by correlation coefficient of .051 and .090 with the p- value of .006 and .368 respectively.

Administrative skills are very significantly related to all the indicators of the performances of elementary schools as evidenced by the obtained coefficient correlation of .344, .368, .357, and .358 with the p-value of .000 of all components, which are lower than 0.05 level of significance.

The administrative culture within a public school can have a significant impact on the performance of its principal. Administrative culture refers to the shared values, beliefs, and practices that guide decision making and behavior within a school. This culture can either support or hinder the effectiveness of a school principal in carrying out their duties (Szabo et al., 2022). A positive and supportive administrative culture can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation among school principals, which in turn can result in improved performance. Principals who feel supported and valued by their colleagues and superiors are more likely to take risks and make innovative decisions, as well as to engage in effective communication and collaboration. On the other hand, a negative or unsupportive

administrative culture can lead to burnout and low morale among principals, leading to decreased job satisfaction and performance.

Furthermore, the administrative culture within a school can also impact the working conditions and resources available to principals. Schools with a positive administrative culture are more likely to provide the necessary resources and support that principals need to effectively lead their schools. This includes access to professional development opportunities, resources for program and resource allocation, and a supportive network of colleagues and superiors (Thomas, 2020).

Finally, the relationship between administrative culture and the performance of school principals in public schools is a critical one. A positive and supportive administrative culture can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation among principals, which in turn can result in improved performance (Portey, 2021). On the other hand, a negative administrative culture can have a detrimental impact on the performance and well-being of school principals. It is important for education leaders and policymakers to work to create and maintain a supportive and positive administrative culture within public schools, to ensure the effectiveness of school principals and the success of the education system.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn: (1) most of the public elementary school heads are middle-aged, male, married, school principal I, relatively young in their present position as school heads, bachelor's degree holders with MA units, and have limited administrative trainings undertaken; (2) school heads are "Highly Competent" on their instructional leadership along promoting a school-wide professional development as well as on their administrative skills along motivating and inspiring and leading positive change; (3) the public elementary schools of School Division of Ilocos Norte are in "Maturing Level" of practice, (4) the instructional leadership and administrative skills of school heads are significantly related to performance of the elementary schools; (5) school heads are "Moderately Competent" along instructional leadership as to defining and communicating goals and monitoring and providing feedback as well as on their administrative skills along communicating directives, empowering and delegating, managing stress and developing resiliency, managing conflict and building effective teams and teamwork. The results indicate that it is proper to propose a Scaffolding Plan.

References

- Alsaleh, A. A. (2022). The Influence of Heads of Departments' Instructional Leadership, Cooperation, and Administrative Support on School-Based Professional Learning in Kuwait. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 832-850.
- Amadi, C. S. (2023). The integration of 21st-century skills in science: A case study of Canada and the USA. *Education and Urban Society*, 56-87.
- Arghode, V., Lathan, A., Alagaraja, M., Rajaram, K., & McLean, G. N. (2022). Empathic organizational culture and leadership: conceptualizing the framework. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 239-256.
- Azad, N., Anderson, G., & Sobotka, J. L. (2017). Leadership and management are one and the same. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 1-12.
- Burgueno, R., Calderon, A., Sinelnikov, O., & Medina-Casaubon, J. (2022). Development and initial validation of the education scale. *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*, 73-87.
- Chudy, S., Neumeister, P., Koribaska, I., Strouhal, M., & Selicka, D. (2021). Contemplative insight as an opinion conflict and a search for meaning in the context of innovative

- elements of the revolution industry 4.0. *Education and Information Technologies*, 673-682.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2019). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 97-140.
- Gamile, J., & Marpa, E. (2022). School environment and school heads' managerial skills: Looking into their relationships to school's performance. *International Journal on Social and Education Sciences*, 218-235.
- Garcia, T. D. (2018). Distributed leadership and teacher job satisfaction in Singapore. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 127-142.
- Gedifew, M. T. (2023). Instructional Leadership Development Practices in Ethiopia: Curriculum Development and Implementation Practices, and Career Development Frameworks. *Journal of School Leadership*, 50-65.
- Henderson, T. (2017, May 8). *Why innovation is crucial to your organization's long-term success*. Retrieved from Forbes:
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2017/05/08/why-innovation-is-crucial-to-your-organizations-long-term-success/?sh=7a0b16e23098>
- Kaya, M., & Selvitopu, A. (2019). A meta-analysis of the effects of some factors on teachers' classroom management skills. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 409-425.
- Krantz, A., & Downey, S. (2021). Thinking about art: The role of single-visit art museum field trip programs in visual arts education. *Art education*, 37-42.
- Leatherman, J. M. (2022). Collaborative Inclusive Programs: Influences of Administrators and Teacher Leaders. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, 38-50.
- Mansor, A., & Hamid, A. (2022). Challenges and Strategies in Managing Small Schools: A Case Study in Perak, Malaysia. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 694-710.
- OECD. (2016). *Innovating education and educating for innovation: The power of digital technologies and skills*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Portey, A. (2021). An administrator's role in motivating teachers. *BU Journal of Graduate Studies in Education*, 4-7.
- Prachagool, V., & Nuangchalerm, P. (2021). Perspectives of Thai educators toward 21st century instruction. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 432-437.
- Sabag, Z., & Cohen, S. (2022). Adapting the education system to 21st century skills: The case of Israel. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 1911-1921.
- Stasewitsch, E., Dokuka, S., & Kauffeld, S. (2022). Promoting educational innovations and change through networks between higher education teachers. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 61-79.
- Stoll, L. (2019). The school as a learning organization: A review revisiting and extending a timely concept. *Evaluation and Strategic Education*, 1-10.
- Suparman, A., Rohaeti, E., & Wening, S. (2022). Development of Attitude Assessment Instruments towards Socioscientific Issues in Chemistry Learning. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 1947-1958.
- Szabo, E., Korodi, K., Szel, E., & Jagodics, B. (2022). Facing the inevitable: The effects of coronavirus disease pandemic and online teaching on teachers' self-efficacy, workload and job satisfaction. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 151-162.
- Thomas, L. (2020). Transformational school leadership as a key factor for teachers' job attitudes during their first year in the profession. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 106-132.